

Synthesis of some 2,4-Diamino-6-substituted-aminopyrimidines and some related 5-Arylazopyrimidines

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Synthesis of some 2,4-diamino-6-(substituted-amino)pyrimidines (2) and 2,4-diamino-5-(substituted-phenylazo)-6-(substituted-amino)pyrimidines (3) are described. Compounds 2a-e were synthesised by condensation of 2,4-diamino-6-chloropyrimidine (1) with the appropriate aromatic amines, and compounds 3a-u by coupling 2 with diazotised arylamines.

It has been reported that many purine and pyrimidine derivatives¹⁻³ exhibit antagonistic activity on nucleic acid metabolism and reveal antifolic, antineoplastic and antimicrobial activities. The presence of amino groups in C-2 and C-4 positions of the pyrimidine ring⁴ and also the presence of hydroxyl and/or amino groups in C-2 and C-4 positions having a bulky substituted-amino group in C-6 position⁵⁻⁸, with nitro group in C-5 position⁹ have been found to exhibit various biological activities.

In view of the above findings, the present paper describes the synthesis of several analogous compounds having a bulky substituted-amino group in C-6 position (2) along with an arylazo group in C-5 position (3) of the 2,4-diaminopyrimidine moiety.

2,4-Diamino-6-chloropyrimidine^{7,8} was refluxed with a slight excess of the corresponding amine in aqueous ethanol in presence of hydrochloric acid according to the method of Koppel *et al.*⁹, resulting the trisubstituted-pyrimidines 2a and 2c. Compounds 2b, 2d and 2e were similarly prepared, except that the addition of ammonium hydroxide was not necessary after the treatment of norite (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The tetrasubstituted-pyrimidines (3) were synthesised by the reaction of the appropriate trisubstituted-pyrimidines (2) with diazotised aniline or *p*-chloroaniline or *p*-carboxyaniline. The coupling reaction was carried out at 2-10° and at pH 3-4 or 5-6 or 8-9 depending on the nature of 2 used.

Proper maintenance of pH was essential for the reaction (Scheme 2). The compounds were crystallised from appropriate solvents.

Scheme 2

The analytical, physical and spectral data of compounds 2 and 3 are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Anticancer activity evaluation of some of the selected compounds (2 and 3) by National Cancer Institute, U.S.A., are in progress.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a copper block. M.p. of the compounds that melted with decomposition was determined by rapidly heating the block to 20° below the actual m.p. and subsequently at the rate of 4°/min. All the m.p.s. are corrected.

In crystallisation, the term alcohol always refers to aqueous 95% (v/v) ethanol. Absorption spectra of the compound were determined in a Shimadzu 210A double-beam spectrophotometer.

General methods of preparation of the trisubstituted-pyrimidines (2): Method A: To a solution of 2,4-diamino-6-chloropyrimidine (0.0065 mol) in hot water (6 ml), the corresponding aniline (0.0095 mol), ethanol (3.0 ml) and concentrated HCl (3 drops) were added. The solution was refluxed for 4 h and

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2,4,6-TRISUBSTITUTED-PYRIMIDINES (2)

Compd no.	R ₁	Mol. formula	Yield %	Colour	Nature	M.p.** °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ _{max} † nm
							C	H	N	
2a ^a	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	89	White	Needle	175 ^c	58.80 (58.77)	6.10 (6.12)	28.50 (28.57)	245, 285
2b ^b	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	84	White	Plate	950 ^d	53.55 (53.87)	4.44 (4.48)	28.40 (28.57)	198s, 813s
2c ^a	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	88	White	Plate	215 ^e	42.89 (42.85)	4.18 (4.28)	30.20 (30.00)	200s, 257s, 314s
2d ^b	SO ₂ H	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO ₂	85	White	Plate	300 ^f	42.50 (42.70)	3.99 (3.91)	24.90 (24.91)	195s, 220, 308s
2e ^b	NO ₂	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	85	Yellow	Shinning needles	120 ^g	48.88 (48.78)	4.00 (4.06)	29.90 (29.89)	262, 375

* Method of preparation : ^aMethod A, ^bMethod B. ** Solvent for crystallisation : ^caqueous ethanol, ^ddilute acetic acid, ^eacetone, ^fpyridine, ^gethanol. † 2a and 2e in ethanol, 2b and 2d in 0.1 N NaOH, 2c in 0.1 N HCl.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES (3)

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	Yield %	Colour (Nature)	M.p.* °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ _{max} nm
							C	H	N	
3a	OC ₂ H ₅	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	98	Yellow (Shinning needle)	180d ^a	60.00 (60.58)	5.59 (5.63)	29.00 (29.07)	253s, 285s, 400br, 428br
3b	COOH	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	84	Silver brown (Shinning crystal)	310d ^a	56.98 (56.97)	5.97 (4.45)	29.12 (29.08)	250s, 294vi, 310vi, 365br
3c	SO ₂ NH ₂	H	C ₁₀ N ₂ SO ₂	94	Yellow (Shinning plate)	220 ^b	50.00 (50.00)	4.00 (4.16)	29.00 (29.16)	246, 292, 400br
3d	SO ₂ H	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO ₂	90	Deep brown (Crystal)	265d ^c	49.89 (49.87)	3.76 (3.89)	25.70 (25.45)	265, 295, 355i, 405i, 430br
3e	NO ₂	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	80	Deep chocolate (Plate)	189 - 140d ^a	54.45 (54.85)	4.00 (4.00)	32.30 (32.00)	250, 285, 385
3f	Cl	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₂	98	Yellowish brown (Powder)	240 ^a	56.59 (56.55)	4.00 (4.12)	28.96 (28.86)	252s, 298s, 350i, 395i, 420
3g	Br	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ BrN ₂	97	Dull yellow (Shinning needle)	245 ^b	50.00 (50.01)	3.94 (3.64)	25.70 (25.52)	252, 290, 395i, 418i
3h	OC ₂ H ₅	Cl	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ OCl	90	Light brown (Crystal)	185 ^a	54.90 (54.98)	5.00 (5.11)	26.38 (26.37)	246, 280, 440br
3i	COOH	Cl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	94	Yellow (Shinning plate)	200 ^b	51.60 (51.68)	4.00 (4.08)	26.00 (26.37)	245, 292, 425, 400vi
3j	SO ₂ NH ₂	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ SO ₂	45	Brown (Crystal)	120 - 30d ^a	45.00 (45.87)	3.90 (3.82)	26.50 (26.76)	251s, 300, 395, 425i
3k	SO ₂ H	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ SO ₂	75	Chocolate brown (Crystal)	285 - 90d ^c	45.70 (45.76)	3.90 (3.87)	27.00 (28.86)	258s, 300, 343i, 435
3l	NO ₂	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ O ₂	95	Purple (Shinning needle)	200 ^a	49.97 (49.93)	3.65 (3.64)	29.00 (29.12)	250, 270vi, 378
3m	Cl	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂	82	Orange (Crystal)	190d ^a	51.00 (51.83)	3.00 (3.47)	26.40 (26.20)	262s, 345br, 362i
3n	Br	Cl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ BrClN ₂	90	Dull yellow (Needle)	210 ^a	45.90 (45.88)	3.50 (3.64)	23.00 (23.12)	255s, 288, 340, 390i
3o	OC ₂ H ₅	COOH	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	98	Orange (Powder)	280d ^a	57.70 (57.86)	5.00 (5.07)	24.70 (24.87)	225s, 288, 435

(Table 2 contd.)

3p	COOH	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₄	97	Deep brown (Crystal)	290d ^a	54.80 (54.82)	4.00 (4.06)	24.70 (24.86)	252s, 805, 410vi, 435
3q	SO ₂ NH ₂	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂	95	Deep chocolate (Crystal)	275 ^b	51.00 (51.12)	4.56 (4.76)	28.00 (28.07)	251s, 800, 430br
3r	SO ₂ H	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₂	82	Reddish yellow (Crystal)	290-27d ^c	47.44 (47.44)	8.80 (8.72)	22.49 (22.78)	245, 290, 410br
3s	NO ₂	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₄	51	Reddish yellow (Needle)	280 ^b	51.50 (51.64)	8.70 (8.79)	28.10 (28.85)	252s, 280vi, 350
3t	Cl	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₇ O ₄	80	Reddish yellow (Needle)	270d ^b	58.00 (58.05)	9.80 (9.90)	25.42 (25.48)	255s, 294s, 405vi, 430
3u	Br	COOH	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ BrN ₇ O ₄	89	Orange (Crystal)	285d ^b	47.50 (47.56)	8.49 (8.49)	22.80 (22.85)	252s, 295, 435

* Solvent for crystallisation: ^aaqueous ethanol, ^bethanol, ^cpyridine, ^daqueous pyridine. ** s=sharp, br=broad, i=inconspicuous, vi=very inconspicuous.

then diluted with water (25 ml), treated with norite and filtered. The filtrate was cooled to room temperature and made ammoniacal (pH 7-7.5) with 2 N NH₄OH when a precipitate appeared, and kept in a refrigerator for 12 h. The precipitate was then filtered, washed with suitable solvent to remove impurities, dried at 80° and purified by crystallisation.

Method B: It was similar to method A, except that it was not necessary to adjust the pH to 7.5. Compounds 2a and 2d were washed with water to remove unreacted *p*-phenitidine and *p*-sulphanilic acid, respectively. Compounds 2b and 2c were washed with water, ethanol and then with water to remove unreacted *p*-aminobenzoic acid and *p*-sulphanilamide, respectively. Compound 2e was extracted with ether and then washed with ethanol and water to remove *p*-nitroaniline.

General method of preparation of arylazopyrimidines (3): To a suspension of 2,4,6-trisubstituted-pyrimidine (0.004 mol) in water (200 ml), glacial acetic acid (12-20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring until a clear solution was obtained. 2,4-Diamino-6-*p*-sulphoanilopyrimidine and 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-carboxyanilopyrimidine were dissolved by adding 10 N NaOH (10 ml) with constant stirring; 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-nitroanilopyrimidine was dissolved by adding 10 N HCl (10 ml). The solution was cooled in ice-water and a cold solution of an equimolar amount of the diazotised arylamine (prepared by adding a cold solution of 0.004 mol NaNO₂ in 10 ml water with stirring to an ice-cold solution of 0.004 mol amine in 20 ml 1 N HCl; the diazotised solution containing excess of HCl) was added slowly with stirring (5 min). Then 2 N NaOH solution was added to it dropwise to bring pH of the solution to 8-9 when precipitate appeared. Stirring was continued further for 4 h. In case of compounds 3r and 3d, addition of 2 N NaOH was not necessary; in case of 3b-c, 3e, 3i-j, 3k-1 and 3p,

pH was adjusted to 5-7 by adding 1 N NaOH or 1 N HCl; and for 3n, pH was adjusted to 3-4 by adding 1 N HCl and stirring continued for 4 h. In case of compounds 3b, 3d, 3i and 3n-s, the solution became coloured instead of giving precipitate. In such cases, after stirring for 4 h, pH was adjusted to 3-4 for compounds 3i, 3p, 3r and 3s, to 5-7 for 3d, 3o and 3q, to 8-9 for 3b and 3n by adding 1 N HCl or 1 N NaOH when a heavy precipitate appeared. The mixture was kept in a refrigerator for 12 h and the crude product filtered, washed several times with water, dried at 80° and purified by crystallisation.

Uv spectra: The arylazopyrimidines having an arylamino group at C-6 showed a strong absorption band in the region 274-292 nm and those having saturated substituted-amino group at C-6 at 240-275 nm. All the compounds, however, exhibited an additional high intensity band in the region 386-442 nm, being responsible for their colour.

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